

Author tool support for AR7 based on provenance and Complex Citation

Versions:

2025-01-23: initial draft, Martina Stockhause

2025-04-14: update of AR6 Pilot Implementation, Martina Stockhause

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(<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15714122>)

Introduction/Motivation

The IPCC FAIR Guidelines enhanced the traceability of the AR6 by the archival of all final datasets of the SPMs. WGI's implementation archived all final datasets and figure creation codes, for which the data/code was provided. References to final data and code were added to the report. As part of the finalization of the AR6, references to a Complex Citation object have been added in the metadata for final and input datasets as pilot implementation of the related Complex Citation Working Group of the Research Data Alliance (RDA). An example for a Complex Citation is available in Zenodo:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14986318>, the implementation [code is published as part of the IPCC WGI Github repo](#). The Complex Citation Object provides information on input datasets and codes including DOI references. It functions as short notation for the access of figure creation information (provenance) and the credit assignment to data and software providers.

For a full and easy traceability of the figure creation process by readers and data users as well as by machines and scripts, this Complex Citation object needs to be standardized as well as made accessible with the figure by including it into the figure captions. The first requires a collaboration with the RDA Complex Citation WG and the implementation into the IPCC process.

In AR6 WGI the required detailed information on the figure creation was only provided for the figures of some chapters and the information was sometimes of low quality. The effort to provide the information was too high for many chapters. In order to receive more complete and accurate information on the figure creation, authors need to be provided with tools or frameworks, which writes the information in a standardized form to be submitted through the established IPCC tools and utilized in the report's editorial phase.

Relevant technical standards

References to papers or data are based on relations between Persistent Identifiers (PIDs). The PID type "DOI" is commonly used for the unique identification of papers, data and software. For the traceability and ideally the reproducibility of data products like final datasets, this is not sufficient. It needs to be extended by provenance information, which describes how different input datasets are used by a piece of software/code to generate the final dataset.

The common standard for provenance information is [W3C PROV](#), which is implemented as a variety of specific profiles. The Complex Citation approach combines the idea of references, which enable credit assignment, and provenance in a flexible metadata object called “Complex Citation object” containing a list of objects identified (preferable) by DOIs (see RDA Complex Citation WG¹ recommendations at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14106602> and IPCC use case at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7684260>).

Community tools and frameworks

In [AR6 WGI](#), at least 3 chapters (3, 9, 10) generated their figures with the [ESMValtool](#). This community framework writes provenance records in the W3C standard, which include most of the information required by the Complex Citation. Within the [CMIP Rapid Evaluation Framework \(REF\) project for the AR7 Fasttrack](#) simulations, ESMValtool and other community evaluation frameworks are harmonized. The ESMValtool core, which among other functionalities generates the W3C PROV records, is used for REF. Therefore, a collaboration with REF on extending the W3C PROV profile by the missing information required by the Complex Citation approach is planned to enable several chapters to provide traceability information “on the fly” or without additional effort. A W3C PROV template agreed within REF can be provided for authors not using or not only using REFs to provide their provenance information.

Other chapters write their own code, several use Jupyter notebooks to document the figure generation process². Therefore a collaboration with the [Jupyter project](#) is investigated. The contact was established together with an initial exchange at AGU 2024. Enabling Jupyter notebook to generate Complex Citation objects has the potential of supporting many chapters across all three WGs.

IPCC Context: procedure and established tools

The state of discussion of the AR7 workflows as discussed at the TG-Data F2F 2024 are shown in Figure 1.

¹ Further information at [RDA Complex Citation WG](#), which started at the [AGU Data Citation Community of Practice](#)

² In AR6 WGI Jupyter notebooks were used at least in SPM, chapters 4, 5, 6, 7, 9, 11, 12 and 13/Atlas (<https://github.com/IPCC-WG1>).

Figure 1: AR7 workflows as agreed on TG-Data F2F 2024; A) shows the author workflow, B) and C) the data archival workflows.

* CCO updates/new versions will also be required in the Errata & Corrigenda phase.

Figure 2: Provenance/Complex Citation workflow draft (under discussion).

The Complex Citation implementation targets at

- **"Code"**: REF and Jupyter as target frameworks are to be enabled to provide the "Metadata & Provenance" or Complex Citation object

- **"Figure Assets (stored in figure manager)"**: The Complex Citation object needs to be persistently stored and referenced from the Figure Manager
- **Editorial Processes** (not specified in Figure 1):
 - *AR7 (TSU)*: Register DOI for Complex Citation objects (CCOs; Figure 2) for each figure and include it in figure captions and on the report's figure pages
 - *DDC*: Provide Complex Citation metadata to repositories
 - for inclusion as references in the metadata and
 - for selection of the input data subset to be long-term preserved in the DDC.

Figure 2: Complex Citation Object (CCO) examples for AR7, to be referenced in figure captions.

Tasks

1. Complex Citation object
 - a. Define Complex Citation object standard jointly with RDA Complex Citation WG
 - b. Define IPCC's profile of a Complex Citation object
 - c. Complex Citation object generation from provenance records of notebooks, REF and of the potential Interactive Atlas (IA) and provision of W3C PROV template for authors not using REF nor Jupyter Notebooks
 - d. Machine-access of Complex Citation object linked objects
2. Complex Citation in the IPCC process
 - a. DDC Partner storing provenance records, assigning PIDs and providing API for Complex Citation provider (2b)
 - b. DDC Partner/[DataCite] Registration agency registering Complex Citation objects and providing API for TSU and DDC Partners [DOI might not be registered during editorial process]
 - c. Figure Manager link to provenance storage (2a)
 - d. TSU's editorial process: generation of Complex Citation object out of provenance record, registration through

- Complex Citation provider, and integration into figure captions
- e. DDC Partners' data archival process: add Complex Citation reference to metadata
- 3. Tests
 - a. Independent component tests of responsible partners
 - b. Test of whole workflow by DDC Partners and TSU
 - c. Test by "friendly authors" for REF and Jupyter use cases
- 4. Training material and showcases

Timeline

Rough timeline (2025-03-19):

(Sources: approved schedules of WGI / II / III and [AR7 Training: Delivery Workflow](#))

1. until 2026-09: development phase
2. 10/2026-12/2027: test and training phase, and
3. 01/2028-12/2028: application phase (WGI) and a bit longer for support of WGII/WGIII/SYR

Timeline and specifications (under development): [Provenance Record / Complex Citation Object specification](#)

Risks and Fallbacks

Risk	Impact	Likelihood	Fallback
<p>Complex Citation approach: Complex Citation Object registration not possible</p>	<p>No improvement for traceability and input data credit assignment</p>	<p>moderate: There is interest from several domains in the implementation including NIH. The Complex Citation is primarily not a technical but a community uptake challenge.</p>	<p>AR6 WGI approach: using provenance information to extract code and final data links for display on figure pages</p>
<p>Complex Citation approach: Complex Citation Object not supported by indexers</p>	<p>No or not correct credit assignment for input data providers (task of RDA Complex Citation WG)</p>	<p>difficult to estimate: In case the indexers do not support the Complex Citation approach, the impact of input datasets and credit for them is not assigned.</p>	<p>None required: It does not impact the implementation. IPCC could approach the report publisher (Cambridge University Press) for support in discussions with indexers.</p>
<p>Provenance records: not implemented in key author tools and frameworks</p>	<p>Complex Citation Object cannot be minted</p>	<p>moderate: Both groups approached are interested to work with IPCC DDC on this. The technical implementation is not complicated.</p>	<p>Use SR Cities approach: for gathering information on final data and code, e.g. GitHub metadata or Figure Manager, and display of links on figure pages</p>

Risk	Impact	Likelihood	Fallback
<p>Provenance records: not provided because of usage of other tools or just not uploading the information</p>	<p>Information not sufficient to create a Complex Citation Object</p>	<p>expected to occur for part of the figures: Authors are open for recommendations provided by the TSU but some will not be able to provide the information</p>	<p>Use SR Cities approach: for gathering information on final data and code, e.g. GitHub metadata or Figure Manager, and display of links on figure pages</p>
<p>Provenance records: not standardized and difficult to use</p>	<p>Information use cannot be fully automated</p>	<p>expected to occur to some extent: Authors are willing to comply with recommendations but experience is that a deviation occurs. Training and communication can minimize the extent.</p>	<p>Semi-automated approach required: to deal with un- or partly standardized provenance records</p>
<p>Provenance records: not stored with a PID (or persistent Url)</p>	<p>Provenance records of figures cannot be identified, uniquely</p>	<p>low: under control of DDC Partners/TSU to provide at least unique urls</p>	<p>Pool of provenance records for internal access</p>
<p>Complex Citation Object: no repository available for minting the DOIs and curation the (brief) metadata</p>	<p>No inclusion of Complex Citation Objects in figure captions possible</p>	<p>low: not difficult to implement</p>	<p>Use SR Cities approach enhanced by information on input data from provenance records</p>

Risk	Impact	Likelihood	Fallback
Complex Citation Object: content=Linked Digital Objects not accessible	Information cannot be used by DDC Partners for data archival and references	low: APIs to access metadata is a common feature for repositories; metadata of the PIDs/DOIs of the Linked Digital Objects can be accessed using known DataCite and crossref APIs	Pool of provenance records for internal access
Provenance records: incomplete, e.g. some Linked Digital Objects not provided or not citable	Provenance information and therefore the information in the Complex Citation Object are incomplete	expected to occur to some extent: It is known that some input data is not citable (CORDEX, CMIP5, CMIP7), therefore no DOI reference can be provided. In other cases no dataset PIDs are available	None required